

IMPROVING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION TEACHERS AND ORGANIZING PRACTICAL TRAINING LESSONS IN A DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract: In this scientific article, the theoretical analysis of the training of future technology education teachers and the organization of practical training classes on the basis of innovative digital educational technologies was considered.

Key words: Education, innovation, practical training, student, pedagogue, lesson, professional competence, professional ability, technology, "Technological education".

Introduction.

Today, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the policy of fundamental reform of all sectors is underway. We know that the decisions and decrees issued in the fields when we gained independence cannot meet the requirements of today's times. Currently, as the world is rapidly developing and progressing, it is necessary for us to keep up with the times. I will not be mistaken if I say that it is happening with the fair policies and initiatives of our president, including in order to fundamentally reform the education sector. The only way to do this is to study the decisions and decrees of the developed countries of the world on Education No. 637 dated September 23, 2020, and adapt them to our nation and our nation and with this, the way of development of developed countries is reflected in the reforms in our country. Education and upbringing of the young generation, formation of knowledge, skills and qualifications in the basics of science is considered one of the priority tasks of the state policy. An important condition for the development of the society is determined by the perfection of the personnel training system, advancement on the basis of modern science, culture, economy, techniques and technologies.

The main goal of the article is to reveal the methods of continuous improvement of the professional competence of future technology teachers and the effective use of innovative technologies in the organization of practical training.

These tasks, first of all, involve educating the young generation, who are the creators of the future, to serve their country and people diligently as highly qualified personnel, to work honestly for the development and happiness of a prosperous country. After all, the current era is in great need of selfless, highly qualified teachers who are devoted to the interests of the Motherland.

In addition, opportunities for education of schoolchildren are being created on a large scale this year, new generation school textbooks will be published in large circulation, fiction literature will be published in mother tongue and English for additional reading, and they are being implemented. The meaningful organization of free time of school-age and teenage

children, as well as the content, scope, and weight of educational activities conducted in various additional educational institutions have been improved.

All this cannot be done without modern, enterprising, high professional teachers. After all, in the current conditions, the issues related to providing children with thorough education, the rational organization of children's free time in educational and educational centers working with children, and further strengthening the cooperation of families, neighborhoods, and educational institutions are highly professional from coaches and teachers. requires skill and competence.

As stated in the Law of September 23, 2020 "On Education" No. 637, an individual approach to each student serves to ensure the effectiveness of education, which is a teacher's professional is directly related to competence.

In fact, the need to train a new generation of high-potential, competitive teachers in the field of education is increasing. One of the steps taken by general secondary education institutions to prepare students to work effectively in various sectors of the national economy, to consciously choose professional classifications, is the attention to the development of the science of technology. A clear sign of this is the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 11, 2022 No. PF-134 "On the approval of the national program for the development of public education in 2022-2026" which will have a major impact on public education starting today. It is causing changes.

Highly skilled, competitive specialists are of priority in ensuring large-scale social and economic development in our country. For this purpose, in the following years, great attention is paid to the fundamental reform of the education system in our republic, to the training of specialists who can work with high efficiency in various sectors of the national economy. In this regard, the need to use the experiences of developed countries has become a priority issue in our country. The creation of new textbooks using the Finnish educational system is a clear manifestation of this. In this, methods are updated, in particular, STEAM, SMART, and international assessment criteria PISA, TIMSS and PIRLS. In order to increase the professional competence of teachers, it is necessary to implement the effective use of STEAM and SMART system methods. Using these methods, textbooks and educational literature will help us to achieve our goals. Also, STEAM PARKS and SMART rooms are being organized in educational institutions.

In particular, since great attention is paid to the science of technology in our country, now we have a number of tasks to prepare future teachers of technology education. They are as follows:

- Improving the pedagogical skills of technology education teachers;
- Improving the professional ability of technology education teachers;
- Further improvement of professional competence of technology education teachers;
- To strengthen the creativity of technology education teachers;
- To further increase the creative pedagogical knowledge, skills and qualifications of technology education teachers;
- To ensure that teachers of technology education conduct lessons on the basis of innovative technologies;
- Increasing the use of interactive methods in the process of teaching technology education teachers.

Considering such tasks and applying them to real life is one of the urgent issues of today. Only then can we prepare mature personnel with intellectual potential.

Now let's define the main words of the above tasks. Pedagogical technology - (*UNESCO definition*) - creation, application and integration of teaching and learning methods, human potential and technical. It is the optimal process of acquiring knowledge by using all the possibilities of the means.

The new pedagogical technology is the only system that includes the optimal management of the educational process, which determines the goals of education, creates a plan of the educational process, and ensures the improvement of educational efficiency with the help of their introduction.

Innovation - the process and activity of implementing renewal, change (*in English innovation - introduced innovation, invention*).

Innovative education is a process that prepares a future specialist to work in new conditions, and it consists in making effective new approaches to improving education based on previous knowledge.

Creativity - (*lat. ing. "create" - creation, "creative" - creator*) - the creative ability of an individual that describes the preparation for the production of new ideas and is part of talent as an independent factor. It would not be wrong to say that creativity is a factor that requires a new approach. Because from year to year, with the ideas of creativity and creativity, the burden of humanity is becoming lighter, the hardships are becoming easier and the discomfort is becoming more comfortable. Of course, it covers all spheres and does not leave the sphere of education.

Creative pedagogy is a creative, new, creative approach aimed at organizing the process of education and upbringing, creative thinking, developing abilities and skills aimed at solving existing pedagogical problems.

Practical training is a logical continuation of the educational process, and this term is a general concept of students' independent classroom work.

Technology education classes cannot be imagined without practical training. Because our lessons are closely related to practice. In the organization of practical training, we must use new methods, techniques, methods and innovations while being aware of the current global changes. In this regard, scientists of this field are conducting research and achieving high results.

For example, the 6th grade "Technology and design" course, I-quarter 7-8 topic "Function, application, structure and main parts of a lathe-screw cutting machine. In the case of "organizing the workplace of a turner and locksmith", we will organize the lesson on the basis of innovative technologies, and this, in turn, will help in the development of the teacher's professional competence.

We have chosen a practical lesson. Now we will get acquainted with the purpose and task of the training, the content of the educational process.

Purpose: to teach students the rules of working on a lathe-screw cutting machine and the correct organization of workplaces using innovative technologies, and this, in turn, helps to improve the professional competence of students.

Duties:

- to acquaint students with the functions and areas of application of the lathe-screw cutting machine;

- teaching students the structure and main parts of the lathe-screw cutting machine;
- introducing the workplace of a turner and a locksmith and the requirements for it;
- teach compliance with the rules of safety equipment during training;
- introducing professions related to the service sector.

Content of the educational process:

Teaching knowledge about the function, application, structure and main parts of the lathe-screw cutting machine and the principle of operation; organizing the workplace of a turner and locksmith; to follow the rules of safety equipment, to keep the workplace clean and to form the skills of working on the machine; introducing professions related to the service sector.

In this place, we will also look at the technologies of organizing the educational process, Form: practical training, conversation-lecture, small group or individual work.

Method: "Interactive" (video clips), "Brainstorming" (with the participation of slides), working with text, question-and-answer, exchange of ideas, cluster, group presentation.

Tools: computer equipment, video projector, slides on the topic, lathe-screw cutting machine, handouts.

Supervision: observation, question-and-answer, interesting assignments.

Assessment: non-standard (non-traditional) assessment, incentive or penalty, rating system of assessment.

In order to avoid misunderstandings about non-standard i.e. non-traditional assessment in the above points, we will give information about it.

Non-standard assessment is an assessment that exists in the educational system of Malaysia, Germany and the US states, and it is used to develop creative thinking, creative ability of students, innovative education and professional competence of teachers. In this, the teacher prepares questions related to the topic. Tells students the answers. Students are proud of it and give answers when asked questions. The teacher says that he wants to hear an additional answer. Although this is vital, when students say words or phrases with the meaning of simile, they give the best value to the most unusual and unconventional answer. Because the students who gave vital but unusual and non-traditional answers will become creative thinkers in the future.

Now for the expected results,

Teacher: by providing complete information on the subject, he increases his professional competence and students' knowledge and creativity. Different methods used in the training, interesting assignments on practical work are based on innovative technologies. Increases students' knowledge, skills and abilities.

Student: acquires new knowledge on the subject. Moral and moral qualities related to work and professional education and knowledge and skills on choosing the right profession are formed.

Future plans:

Teacher: mastering professional competence (pedagogical) and innovative technologies, applying them to the teaching process, improving, working on oneself, improving pedagogical skills.

Student: repeat the topic once again, prepare for debate. Preparing a "cluster" and, most importantly, feeling free in class, expressing your thoughts without fear.

We believe that the following considerations should be followed in the organization of technology education classes and practical training using innovative technologies and in improving the professional competence of the teacher:

- to ensure implementation of education in a situation that is highly approximated to real life;
- completely reform the skills of using innovative technologies in education;
- connecting theoretical information with practical activities and allowing students to be involved in the process of active independent learning;
- organization of practical lessons within the framework of international requirements and improvement of the professional competence of pedagogues;
- ensuring formation and development of professional and basic skills;
- to ensure the improvement of teachers' qualifications in internationally prestigious universities.

Based on the above, we express the professional competence of future technology education teachers, the purpose of using innovative technologies in practical training as follows: consistent education and training, as a result of conducting practical training on the basis of innovative technologies, intellectual potential, to educate a well-rounded person who thinks creatively and to increase the professional competence of the teacher.

In order to achieve this goal, it is necessary to carry out the following tasks: to find ways to improve the professional competence of technology teachers in the continuous education system, to regularly encourage creative thinking in students by using innovative technologies in the organization of practical training classes. continuously improving, developing and introducing innovative technologies in the education of students, taking into account their age and outlook.

In conclusion, today we need to pay more attention to the issue of personnel in educational institutions. In particular, the development of technology education is the demand of the times. Technology plays an important role in the education of the young generation. Therefore, our youth is our future, let's not be indifferent to our future.

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